

MEDICAL SCIENCES

PHYSIOLOGY AND GENETICS OF TENSION HEADACHE

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ABSTRACT

Tension-type headache (TTH) is the most common type of primary headache. Also sometimes referred to as "muscle contraction headache," "stress headache," or "psychomyogenic headache, patients often report significant muscle tenderness with increasing headache frequency and intensity. TTH occurs repetitively and may be categorized into episodic TTH, with frequent and infrequent subtypes, and chronic TTH. The differentiating factor for these types is the frequency of headache episodes.

Keywords: stress, headache, physiology, genetics.

Tension-type headache (TTH) is the most common type of primary headache. Also sometimes referred to as "muscle contraction headache," "stress headache," or "psychomyogenic headache, patients often report significant muscle tenderness with increasing headache frequency and intensity. TTH occurs repetitively and may be categorized into episodic TTH, with frequent and infrequent subtypes, and chronic TTH. The differentiating factor for these types is the frequency of headache episodes [1].

Core Risk Factors: Evidence favoring a central origin of a tension headache attack includes both psychosomatic factors and sleep disturbances that would favor activation of structures within the central nervous system at the onset of and during a tension headache attack [2].

Psychosomatic Factors: Imaging studies in patients with TTH have suggested a fundamental role for the anterior cingulate cortex and the insula, both areas recognized for contributing to the cognitive and affective processing of sensory information [3]. In this regard, stress remains one of the most commonly recognized precipitating psychosomatic factors in the onset of a TTH attack. Furthermore, it has been shown that cognitive stress can increase muscle pain in TTH patients compared to controls [4]. Physiologically, stress can trigger or aggravate headache by increasing muscle contraction, releasing catecholamines and cortisol, peripherally sensitizing, and/or affecting central pain processing. The long-term release of corticosteroids in those patients with chronic stress could cause tissue

damage and an increase in pain perception [5]. In TTH, stress has been shown to trigger higher rates of pericranial muscle pain compared to controls. However, and contrary to this theory, there are authors who have not found a relationship between stress and the alteration of the diffuse nociceptive inhibitory control, so the pathophysiological mechanism by which stress can act as a trigger for TTH and its role with respect to the limbic system and supraspinal mechanisms has not yet been elucidated. Likewise, there is no evidence to support a relationship between stress and increased pericranial EMG activity in patients with TTH, so its role in the pathophysiology of TTH remains uncertain [6]. Therefore, the pathophysiological mechanism by which stress can act as a trigger for TTH and its role with respect to the limbic system and supraspinal mechanisms have not yet been elucidated [7]. Likewise, there is no evidence to support a relationship between stress and increased pericranial EMG activity in patients with TTH, so its role in the pathophysiology of TTH remains uncertain. Therefore, the pathophysiological mechanism by which stress can act as a trigger for TTH and its role with respect to the limbic system and supraspinal mechanisms have not yet been elucidated. Likewise, there is no evidence to support a relationship between stress and increased pericranial EMG activity in patients with TTH, so its role in the pathophysiology of TTH remains uncertain [8].

Pathophysiology: Multiple theories have been proposed for the presumed pathophysiology of TTH, but the exact mechanism is unknown. Both central and

peripheral sensitization processes were observed to be clearly involved. Patients with episodic TTH demonstrate higher levels of peripheral excitability, while individuals with chronic TTH clearly show manifestations of central sensitization. Functional magnetic resonance imaging (fMRI) studies investigated the pathophysiology of TTH, focusing on central mechanisms. The findings consistently showed a significant increase in white matter hyperintensity in patients with TTH and identified the potential involvement of various brain areas related to pain perception. These areas included cortical regions (anterior and posterior cingulate cortex, prefrontal cortex, and anterior and posterior insular cortex), subcortical sites (thalamus, caudate, putamen, and parahippocampus), and the cerebellum. However, no significant association was found between TTH and intracranial abnormalities or total intracranial volume [9].

Some reviews on the peripheral origins of TTH discussed initial events occurring outside the brain barrier, suggesting that vascular and musculoskeletal factors play a role at the onset of a tension headache attack. These factors may contribute to the sensitization of the peripheral nervous system due to sustained sensory input.

Another study found that TTH showed less activation at the start of sternocleidomastoid muscle contraction. No association was noted between the presence of a headache and alterations in longus colli muscle dimensions, median frequency, or sternocleidomastoid muscle activation toward the end of contraction [10].

Myofascial trigger points (MTrPs) have been implicated in the possible pathogenesis of TTH and are considered vital treatment components. Trigger points are specific areas, usually located in skeletal muscles. Pressure on these sites may elicit pain in the area and related regions of the body. For TTH, the pericranial musculature is the presumed trigger point. Excessive pericranial muscle contractions may lead to ischemia and the release of noxious substances, such as substance P, which may cause further pain. Over time, these trigger points may become latent, radiating pain only with palpation, or active, causing constant pain. Osteopathic studies suggest that tightening of the suboccipital and upper neck musculature can lead to a "pull" of the dural matter, forming the myodural bridges, which can be very painful [11].

Pharmacological modalities: Chronic TTH develops from episodic TTH, presenting with daily or very frequent headache episodes that last for hours or may become continuous. Various interventions have been reviewed, addressing the effectiveness and safety of non-drug treatments such as acupuncture and cognitive behavioral therapy being used alongside drug therapies, including amitriptyline, anticonvulsants like sodium valproate, topiramate, and gabapentin, benzodiazepines, botulinum toxin, noradrenergic and specific serotonergic antidepressants like mirtazapine, NSAIDs such as ibuprofen, opioid analgesics like codeine, paracetamol, serotonin reuptake inhibitor antidepressants [selective serotonin reuptake inhibitors (SSRIs) and serotonin-norepinephrine reuptake inhibitors (SNRIs)], and tricyclic antidepressants (TCAs) other amitriptyline [12,13].

The primary goal of chronic TTH therapy is to reduce headache frequency through preventive medications. Among pharmacologic treatments, the TCA amitriptyline is the most effective and well-studied. Amitriptyline should be initiated at a low dose (10 to 25 mg daily) and gradually increased (10 to 25 mg weekly) until a therapeutic response is achieved or adverse effects appear, which commonly include dry mouth, drowsiness, urinary retention, cardiac arrhythmias, and glaucoma. The therapeutic response usually occurs in 3 to 4 weeks. In responsive patients, amitriptyline is typically continued for at least 6 months, with withdrawal attempted afterward. Long-term use may be necessary if the headaches recur upon discontinuation [14].

The efficacy of other antidepressants, such as mirtazapine and venlafaxine, has been documented. Weaker evidence backs the efficacy of gabapentine, topiramate, and tizanidine. Research also demonstrated that SSRIs and SNRIs were not as effective as TCAs. Recent studies did not provide high-quality evidence supporting the use of SSRIs or the SNRI venlafaxine as preventive drugs for TTH. SSRIs or venlafaxine were no more effective than placebo or amitriptyline in reducing headache frequency in patients with chronic TTH after 2 months of treatment. SSRIs were also found to be less effective than TCAs in terms of analgesic medication use. However, TCAs were associated with more adverse events [15].

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